

Table S1. Synonymous keywords merging in Citespace analysis.

Keywords	Replaced by
1st hemorrhage	1st variceal hemorrhage
nonselective beta blocker	beta blocker
nonselective beta-blocker	beta blocker
consortstatement	consort statement
computed tomography	ct
transjugularintrahepatic portosystemic shunt	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
tip	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
intrahepaticportosystemic shunt	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
portacaval shunt	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
portosystemic shunt	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
portosystemic stent shunt	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt
hepatic encephalopathy	encephalopathy
hepatitis c virus	hepatitis c
hcv related cirrhosis	chronic hepatitis c
isosorbide 5 mononitrate	isosorbide mononitrate
isosorbide dinitrate	isosorbide mononitrate
isosorbidemononitrate	isosorbide mononitrate
intra arterialvasopressin	intra arterial vasopressin
secondary prophylaxi	secondary prevention
variceal rebleeding	recurrent variceal hemorrhage
improvedsurvival	improved survival
chronic liver disease	cirrhosis
cirrhotic patient	cirrhosis
cirrhotics	cirrhosis
hepatic cirrhosis	cirrhosis
liver cirrhosis	cirrhosis
acute variceal hemorrhage	acute variceal bleeding
bleeding varice	variceal hemorrhage
variceal bleeding	variceal hemorrhage
variceal haemorrhage	variceal hemorrhage
alcoholic cirrhotic patient	alcoholic cirrhosis
alcoholiccirrhosis	alcoholic cirrhosis
alcoholiccirrhotic patient	alcoholic cirrhosis
controlledclinical trial	controlled clinical trial
hypertension portal	portal hypertension
endoscopic treatment	endoscopic therapy
retrograde transvenous obliteration	trans hepatic obliteration
balloontamponade	balloon tamponade
oralpropranolol	oral propranolol
2 octyl cyanoacrylate	butyl cyanoacrylate
cyanoacrylate injection	butyl cyanoacrylate
2 octylcyanoacrylate	butyl cyanoacrylate
cyanoacrylate	butyl cyanoacrylate
n butyl 2 cyanoacrylate	butyl cyanoacrylate
n butyl 2 cyanoacrylate injection	butyl cyanoacrylate

upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage	upper gastrointestinal bleeding
survival analysis	survival
oesophageal varice	esophageal varice
bleeding oesophageal varice	bleeding esophageal varice
esophageal variceal bleeding	bleeding esophageal varice
riskeoesophageal varice	risk esophageal varice
gastroesophageal varice	esophagogastric varice
gastroesophageal variceal bleeding	esophageal and gastric varice
randomized clinical trial	controlled randomized trial
randomized controlled trial	controlled randomized trial
randomizedcontrolled trial	controlled randomized trial
randomizedtrial	randomized trial
banding ligation	band ligation
bandligation	band ligation
endoscopic band ligation	band ligation
endoscopic ligation	band ligation
endoscopic variceal ligation	band ligation
endoscopicband ligation	band ligation
ligation	band ligation
terlipressin	glypressin
terlipressin glypressin	glypressin
terlipressin	glypressin
terlipressin glypressin	glypressin
gastrointestinal haemorrhage	gastrointestinal bleeding
gastrointestinal hemorrhage	gastrointestinal bleeding
gastric fundal varice	fundal varice
gastric varix	gastric varice
gastricvarice	gastric varice
propranolol plusisorbide 5 mononitrate	propranolol plus isosorbide 5 mononitrate
pharmacological therapy	medical therapy
pharmacological treatment	medical therapy
endoscopic injection sclerotherapy	endoscopic sclerotherapy
endoscopicsclerotherapy	endoscopic sclerotherapy
sclerotherapy	endoscopic sclerotherapy
injection sclerotherapy	endoscopic sclerotherapy
injectionsclerotherapy	endoscopic sclerotherapy
prophylactic sclerotherapy	prophylactic endoscopic sclerotherapy
prophylacticsclerotherapy	prophylactic endoscopic sclerotherapy
long termmanagement	long term management

Table S2. Excluded keywords in the Citespace analysis.

Excluded Keywords
cirrhosis
portal hypertension
hemorrhage
gastroesophageal varice
liver cirrhosis
variceal hemorrhage

Table S3. Synonymous keywords merging in VOS analysis.

Keywords	Replaced by
beta-blockers	beta-blocker
nonselective beta-blockers	beta-blocker
computed-tomography	ct
hvpq	hepatic venous pressure gradient
postprandial splanchnic hyperemia	hepatic venous pressure gradient
meld	meld score
meta-analysis	metaanalysis
graft portacaval shunts	tips
intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	tips
intrahepatic portosystemic shunts	tips
intrahepatic-portosystemic shunt	tips
portacaval-shunt	tips
portosystemic shunt	tips
portosystemic stent-shunt	tips
tipss	tips
transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	tips
placebo	placebo-controlled trial
hemorrhage	bleeding
isosorbide-5-mononitrate	isosorbide mononitrate
controlled-trial	controlled trial
secondary prophylaxis	secondary prevention
rebleeding	recurrence
recurrent variceal hemorrhage	recurrence
hepatocellular-carcinoma	hepatocellular carcinoma
liver-disease	liver disease
encephalopathy	hepatic encephalopathy
hepatic-encephalopathy	hepatic encephalopathy
liver-transplantation	liver transplantation
chronic liver-disease	cirrhosis
chronic liver disease	cirrhosis

cirrhotic-patients	cirrhosis
cirrhotics	cirrhosis
hepatic cirrhosis	cirrhosis
liver cirrhosis	cirrhosis
liver-cirrhosis	cirrhosis
high-risk patients	high-risk
acute variceal hemorrhage	acute variceal bleeding
bleeding varices	variceal bleeding
variceal band ligation	variceal bleeding
variceal haemorrhage	variceal bleeding
variceal hemorrhage	variceal bleeding
alcoholic cirrhotic-patients	alcoholic cirrhosis
clinical-trials	clinical-trial
hypertension	portal hypertension
hypertension, portal	portal hypertension
portal-hypertension	portal hypertension
portal-vein thrombosis	portal vein thrombosis
portal-vein thrombosis	portal vein thrombosis
endoscopic treatment	endoscopic therapy
balloon tamponade	balloon-occluded retrograde transvenous obliteration
prospective randomized-trial	prospective controlled trial
cyanoacrylate injection	cyanoacrylate
butyl cyanoacrylate	cyanoacrylate
n-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate	cyanoacrylate
n-butyl-2-cyanoacrylate injection	cyanoacrylate
upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage	upper gastrointestinal bleeding
esophageal-varices	esophageal varices
oesophageal varices	esophageal varices
bleeding esophageal varices	esophageal variceal bleeding
bleeding esophageal-varices	esophageal variceal bleeding
gastroesophageal varices	esophagogastric varices
esophageal and gastric varices	esophagogastric varices
randomized clinical-trials	randomized controlled trial
randomized controlled-trial	randomized controlled trial
randomized-trial	randomized trial
banding ligation	band ligation
endoscopic band ligation	band ligation
endoscopic ligation	band ligation
endoscopic variceal ligation	band ligation
ligation	band ligation
variceal ligation	band ligation
terlipressin	glypressin
terlipressin glypressin	glypressin
gastrointestinal haemorrhage	gastrointestinal bleeding
gastrointestinal hemorrhage	gastrointestinal bleeding
gastrointestinal-tract hemorrhage	gastrointestinal bleeding
fundal varices	gastric fundal varices
bleeding gastric varices	gastric variceal bleeding

bacterial-infections
pharmacological therapy
pharmacological-treatment
pharmacotherapy
primary prophylaxis
endoscopic injection sclerotherapy
sclerotherapy
injection sclerotherapy
prophylaxis
antibiotic-prophylaxis
prophylactic endoscopic sclerotherapy
term-follow-up
treatment

bacterial-infection
medical therapy
medical therapy
medical therapy
primary prevention
endoscopic sclerotherapy
endoscopic sclerotherapy
endoscopic sclerotherapy
prevention
antibiotic prophylaxis
prophylactic sclerotherapy
term follow-up
therapy

Table S4. Country scientific production, total citations and national development data from top 14 countries. CSP: country scientific production. HEPC: health expenditure per capita in 2019.

Country	CSP	Total citations	Average article citations	GDP2020(current US\$)	Population(2020)	HEPC(2019, current US\$)
USA	487	7561	51.09	20,953,030,000,000.00	329,484,123	10,921.01
Spain	271	4431	66.13	1,281,484,640,043.58	47,351,567	2,711.19
Italy	229	3972	58.41	1,888,709,443,687.48	59,554,023	2,905.50
France	311	3772	41	2,630,317,731,455.26	67,391,582	4,491.74
China	689	3701	21.27	14,722,730,697,890.10	1,410,929,362	535.13
Germany	147	1806	31.68	3,846,413,928,653.71	83,240,525	5,440.25
India	70	1156	42.81	2,660,245,248,867.63	1,380,004,385	63.75
Japan	120	902	19.19	5,057,758,958,706.64	125,836,021	4,360.47
Greece	41	662	44.13	188,835,201,625.91	10,715,549	1,500.59
Canada	45	622	41.47	1,645,423,407,568.36	38,005,238	5,048.37
Denmark	44	514	36.71	356,084,867,685.64	5,831,404	6,003.33
Belgium	70	374	17	521,861,292,586.62	11,555,997	4,960.39
Brazil	37	246	17.57	1,444,733,258,971.65	212,559,409	853.39
Pakistan	37	233	23.3	262,610,002,938.51	220,892,331	39.50

Table S5. Top 10 Citations of Included Records.

Rank	Title	Citations	Pub. Year	Author	source
1	Prevention and management of gastroesophageal varices and variceal hemorrhage in cirrhosis	1037	2007	Garcia-Tsao	Hepatology
2	Portal hypertensive bleeding in cirrhosis: risk stratification, diagnosis, and management: 2016 practice guidance by the American Association for the study of liver diseases	880	2017	Garcia-Tsao	Hepatology
3	The transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic stent-shunt procedure for variceal bleeding	656	1994	Rossle	The New England Journal of Medicine
4	Prediction of the 1st variceal hemorrhage in patients with cirrhosis of the liver and esophageal-varices - a prospective multicenter study	625	1988	De Franchis	The New England Journal of Medicine
5	Current concepts: management of varices and variceal hemorrhage in cirrhosis.	544	2010	Garcia-Tsao	The New England Journal of Medicine
6	Endoscopic sclerotherapy as compared with endoscopic ligation for bleeding esophageal varices	518	1992	Stiegmann	The New England Journal of Medicine
7	Relation between portal pressure response to pharmacotherapy and risk of recurrent variceal hemorrhage in patients with cirrhosis	432	1995	Feu	Lancet
8	Prevention and management of gastroesophageal varices and variceal hemorrhage in cirrhosis	372	2007	Garcia-Tsao	American Journal of Gastroenterology
9	Beta-adrenergic antagonist drugs in the prevention of gastrointestinal-bleeding in patients with cirrhosis and esophageal-varices - an analysis of data and prognostic factors in 589 patients from 4 randomized clinical-trials	371	1991	Poynard	The New England Journal of Medicine
10	Hepatic vein pressure gradient reduction and prevention of variceal bleeding in cirrhosis: a systematic review	312	2006	D'amico	Gastroenterology

Table S6. Cluster labels shown by the log-likelihood ratio (LLR) of keywords. BRTO: balloon-occluded retrograde transvenous obliteration.

Cluster	Keywords(log-likelihood ratio,p-value)
0	transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (29.24, 1.0E-4); esophageal varice (27.2, 1.0E-4); variceal bleeding (25.07, 1.0E-4); injection sclerotherapy (19.58, 1.0E-4); endoscopic sclerotherapy (18.58, 1.0E-4)
1	somatostatin (32.15, 1.0E-4); octreotide (18.34, 1.0E-4); placebo controlled trial (15.47, 1.0E-4); vasopressin (14.69, 0.001); double blind (13.97, 0.001)
2	prophylactic portacaval anastomosis (5.98, 0.05); long term survival (5.32, 0.05); randomized controlled trials (5.32, 0.05); beta blockade (5.32, 0.05); upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage (4.83, 0.05)
3	primary prophylaxi (31.45, 1.0E-4); isosorbide mononitrate (30.56, 1.0E-4); risk esophageal varice (22.6, 1.0E-4); hemodynamic response (21.42, 1.0E-4); propranolol plus isosorbide 5 mononitrate (17.5, 1.0E-4)
4	injection sclerotherapy (46.79, 1.0E-4); bleeding esophageal varice (38.3, 1.0E-4); prospective randomized trial (35.75, 1.0E-4); distal splenorenal shunt (31.98, 1.0E-4); endoscopic sclerotherapy (31.2, 1.0E-4)